

**ASSESSMENT OF GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION
COMPETENCIES AMONG GRADE 5 TO GRADE 12
STUDENTS OF SCUOLA DEI BAMBINI**

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Assessment of Global Citizenship Education Competencies among Grade 5 to Grade 12 Students of Scuola Dei Bambini

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Abstract

This quantitative study aimed to assess the Global Citizenship Education (GCED) competencies of Scuola Dei Bambini students across Grade 5 to Grade 12. Data were collected from 83 respondents using the SEA-PLM questionnaire and analyzed through descriptive comparative statistics. Due to the small population of respondents, a complete enumeration approach was employed. The results indicated no significant differences in GCED competencies based on age, sex, or language spoken. While the majority of respondents reported substantial exposure to GCED topics, their socio-emotional competencies revealed a lack of connection with peers globally, as well as a disagreement with the notion that the world is a fair place. In terms of behavioral competencies, respondents were generally reluctant to voice their opinions on global issues during classroom discussions. Based on these findings, it is recommended to enhance the socio-emotional and behavioral competencies of students, and the implementation of a targeted program is proposed to address these gaps within the school.

Keywords: *global citizenship education, GCED competencies, behavioral competency, cognitive competency, socio-emotional competency*

Introduction

In 2015, world leaders endorsed the Education 2030 Agenda, aiming to revolutionize global education systems. One critical approach highlighted by UNESCO within this agenda is Global Citizenship Education (GCED), designed to tackle pressing global challenges such as poverty, inequality, climate change, and human rights (UNESCO, 2023). As part of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), GCED aligns with Goal 4.7, which stipulates that by 2030, all learners will acquire the knowledge and skills required to promote sustainable development. This includes education for sustainable development, human rights, gender equality, a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and the appreciation of cultural diversity (Perraud, 2021).

While literacy and numeracy are foundational skills, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that they alone are insufficient to understand and address the complex global challenges that transcend national borders. Köllner (2023) further asserts that these skills must be complemented by the competencies fostered through GCED, which aims to equip students with the knowledge, values, and skills to foster solidarity and respect within an interconnected global society. The ultimate goal of GCED is to ensure harmony and mutual respect, transcending boundaries to create a more peaceful world.

However, despite the transformative potential of GCED, it has received limited attention in educational discussions. Bourn (2021) suggests that the discourse around GCED has often been overshadowed, although it offers a vision for the future that emphasizes hope and transformation. Additionally, Wasilewski (2019) identified a significant gap in the practical application of GCED. The study highlights a lack of teacher training on GCED and the absence of its inclusion in teacher preparation programs, pointing out the inadequacy of frameworks for integrating GCED into school curricula. As of now, the typologies of GCED are still narrow and largely undefined (Al'Abri, Ambusaidi, & Alhadi, 2022).

Language plays an essential role in GCED, as it enhances cultural awareness, communication skills, and global competence. Ernst-Slavit and Egbert (2021) assert that language is a key tool for thriving in an interconnected world, enabling learners to connect with different cultures and build meaningful relationships (Manjushree, 2020). Moreover, demographic factors such as age and sex are crucial in ensuring that learners from diverse backgrounds can engage in impactful global learning experiences (DepEd, 2023). GCED seeks to provide learners with the necessary skills, knowledge, behaviors, and values to become responsible global citizens while promoting gender equality and addressing gender-based discrimination and violence (Al'Abri et al., 2022; UNESCO, 2023).

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the Global Citizenship Education (GCED) competencies among Grade 5 to Grade 12 students of Scuola Dei Bambini. The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age; and
 - 1.3. language spoken?
2. What are the respondents' competencies in Global Citizenship Education (GCED) based on the following dimensions:
 - 2.1. cognitive competency;
 - 2.2. socio-emotional competency; and

- 2.3. behavioral competency?
3. Is there a significant difference in the GCED competencies of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic characteristics (sex, age, and language spoken)?
4. Based on the findings of this study, what program can be proposed to enhance the respondents' GCED competencies?

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research approach utilizing a descriptive comparative design to assess the Global Citizenship Education (GCED) competencies among Grade 5 to Grade 12 students of Scuola Dei Bambini in San Pablo City, Laguna. The descriptive comparative design, as defined by Siedlecki (2020), examines population characteristics, identifies issues within a unit or population, and compares variations in characteristics or practices between different groups. This research design is ideal for this study as it involves collecting data from a sample of individuals through questionnaires to describe their characteristics, opinions, and attitudes towards GCED.

The respondents of the study were 83 students from Scuola Dei Bambini di Sta. Teresita International Montessori Incorporated, a private institution in San Pablo City. These students, spanning Grades 5 to 12, were selected based on the premise that students in these grades begin to develop their global citizenship competencies (Bernardo et al., 2022). High school students were also included due to their positive attitudes toward research, as demonstrated in the study by Roxas (2020), where high school students showed a generally favorable stance towards research. Their knowledge, skills, and attitudes are pivotal in shaping their contributions to society.

For sampling, the researcher employed a complete enumeration or census method. With only 83 students in the school for the 2023-2024 academic year, this approach was deemed appropriate as it allows for a full and accurate count of the population. This method is particularly useful for small sample sizes, ensuring precise analysis by including every individual in the population (Abrol, H.S., 2021).

The researcher utilized a questionnaire adapted from the South East Asia – Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019. The SEA-PLM questionnaire, which is publicly available, was used to gather data on the respondents' demographic profile (sex, age, language spoken at home) as well as their competencies in GCED across three domains: cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral competencies. The researcher accessed the questionnaire through the SEA-PLM website after registering and citing the source of the instrument as required. The first section of the questionnaire gathered demographic information, while the second part assessed competencies in the identified GCED domains.

Data collection involved several steps. Initially, the researcher obtained approval from the PLSP president and the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct research outside the university. With this approval, the researcher submitted a request to the school directress of Scuola Dei Bambini for permission to conduct the study. After obtaining permission, a consent form was sent to the parents of the students, informing them of the purpose of the study and seeking their approval for their children's participation. The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents via Google Forms, a method familiar to the students who are accustomed to using personal devices for such activities. During the survey administration, the researcher provided explanations to ensure the respondents fully understood the instructions and questions. The data collected were then recorded, tabulated, and analyzed using statistical methods.

Ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, with respondents informed that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. Parental consent and assent were obtained for the students' participation, ensuring that parents understood the study's objectives and any potential risks. The anonymity of the respondents was maintained, with data collected in a manner that ensured confidentiality. Additionally, the study was conducted with sensitivity to the potential for harm, ensuring that no emotional, physical, or psychological harm would come to the participants. Finally, the results of the study will be communicated to both the respondents and the school administration.

The data gathered were analyzed using several statistical tools. Descriptive statistics, including percentages, were used to determine the distribution of the respondents' demographic characteristics such as age, sex, and language spoken. Frequency distribution was used to assess the respondents' behavioral competencies in GCED. The mean was calculated to evaluate the respondents' cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral competencies. To determine if there were significant differences in GCED competencies based on demographic characteristics, the Kruskal-Wallis test was applied.

Results and Discussion

The demographic profiles of the respondents, as shown in the table, provide valuable insights into the composition of the sample in terms of sex, age, and language spoken.

In terms of sex, there were 47 male respondents (56.6%) and 36 female respondents (43.4%). This indicates a higher number of male participants, though the difference is relatively small, suggesting a balanced representation of both genders in the study.

Regarding age, the respondents varied significantly, with the largest group being those aged 11 years old and below (27.8%), followed by those aged 15 years and above (26.4%). Other age groups included 12 years old (16.9%), 13 years old (12%), and 14 years old (16.9%). This distribution suggests that the sample predominantly consists of students in primary and early secondary education, with a few students on the older end of the spectrum.

Table 1. *Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents*

<i>Demographic Profiles</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	47	56.6
Female	36	43.4
<i>Age</i>		
11 years old and below	23	27.8
12 years old	14	16.9
13 years old	10	12.0
14 years old	14	16.9
15 years old and above	22	26.4
<i>Language Spoken</i>		
Filipino	24	28.9
English	37	44.6
English and Filipino	14	16.9
Others	8	9.6

When it comes to language spoken, the majority of respondents (44.6%) spoke English, making it the dominant language in the study. Filipino was spoken by 28.9% of respondents, while 16.9% of students spoke both English and Filipino. The remaining 9.6% spoke other languages, such as Chinese or Vietnamese.

The findings from this study carry several important implications for the development of Global Citizenship Education (GCED) programs at Scuola Dei Bambini. First, the gender balance suggests that both male and female students are likely to benefit equally from GCED initiatives, but tailored strategies might be needed to address how each gender perceives and interacts with global issues. Future GCED programs should ensure that gender perspectives are included to enhance inclusivity and create a learning environment that caters to the needs of both boys and girls.

Second, the age distribution indicates that younger students, particularly those in Grades 5 and 6, have a strong potential for developing GCED competencies. It is important for educators to integrate age-appropriate global learning experiences that nurture global awareness and responsibility from an early age. Additionally, the relatively low representation of 13-year-olds might suggest a need to explore why certain age groups, such as those in Grade 8, have fewer enrollees and whether there are specific barriers to their participation in GCED programs.

Lastly, the dominance of English as the primary language spoken at home underscores the importance of leveraging this language to connect students with global issues. GCED programs can be enhanced by providing opportunities for students to engage with a wider range of international perspectives, particularly through English-language resources and cross-cultural exchanges. Furthermore, promoting multilingualism can further enrich students' understanding of global citizenship by fostering communication across diverse linguistic and cultural contexts.

Table 2. *GCED Cognitive Competencies*

<i>At school, how much have you learned about the following topics?</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1. What is happening in countries near Philippines	3.02	Some
2. What is happening in the world	3.41	A lot
3. How things that happen in other countries affect the Philippines	2.88	Some
4. Understanding people that are different to you	3.52	A lot
5. How to solve disagreements with classmates peacefully	3.3	A lot
6. How you can help solve problems in your own community	3.01	Some
7. How to protect the environment	3.6	A lot
8. Pollution in the Philippines	3.31	A lot
9. Pollution in places outside your country	3.05	Some
10. Loss of natural resources (water, energy, useable land, etc.)	3.04	Some
11. Climate change	3.37	A lot
Accumulated Total Mean	3.23	A lot

The data presented in Table 2 indicates that the respondents perceived a strong understanding of the topics related to Global Citizenship Education (GCED) Cognitive competencies, with an overall mean score of 3.23. This suggests that the respondents have gained significant knowledge about global issues. They demonstrate an understanding of diverse cultures, the ability to resolve conflicts with peers peacefully, and are aware of critical environmental concerns such as climate change and pollution in the Philippines. Additionally, they have developed an awareness of strategies to protect the environment.

These findings align with the study by Rogayan, D., & Eveyen El Elyonna, D. N. (2019), which revealed that science students in Zambales exhibit a considerable level of awareness regarding environmental issues, including the state of the environment and its challenges. The study also highlighted a moderate correlation between students' strong commitment to addressing environmental issues and their active involvement in activities aimed at solving these problems.

Furthermore, the respondents reported having some knowledge about global events, particularly in countries neighboring the Philippines, and they recognize that these events can affect the Philippines. They also acknowledged the importance of addressing community problems and expressed awareness of environmental issues beyond their own country, such as pollution and the loss of natural resources. In line with this, the Asia-Pacific Centre of Education for International Understanding (APCEIU, 2019) emphasized that by studying such issues, learners can gain a deeper understanding of the principles of sustainable development.

These findings suggest that exposing students to environmental topics such as climate change, pollution, and the loss of natural resources enhances their awareness of both local and global issues. It also highlights the interconnectedness of countries, fostering a better understanding of how events and challenges in other parts of the world can impact their own country. As students become more knowledgeable, they are better equipped to contribute to resolving issues within their communities and to promoting peaceful conflict resolution with classmates. This underscores the importance of continuing to integrate global citizenship education into curricula, as it empowers students to actively engage with the world around them and take steps toward addressing global challenges.

Table 3. *Global Citizenship Education Socio-Emotional Competency*

<i>How much do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements?</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1. I feel I belong to this country, Philippines.	3.05	Agree
2. I think of myself as Asian.	3.34	Strongly Agree
3. I feel connected to the rest of the world.	2.34	Disagree
4. I feel I have a lot in common with other children in the Philippines.	2.41	Disagree
5. I feel I have a lot in common with other children in Asia.	2.41	Disagree
6. I feel I have a lot in common with children in the world outside Asia.	2.33	Disagree
Accumulated Total Mean	2.65	Disagree

The data from Table 3 reveals that respondents disagreed with the notion of feeling connected to other Asian countries, with an overall mean of 2.65. Specifically, they expressed disagreement when asked about sharing similarities with children both within the Philippines and across Asia, as well as with children from other parts of the world. This suggests that Babinian students perceive themselves as distinct from other children, both within their own country and beyond.

This finding indicates a need to enhance their values and attitudes regarding connections with others, both locally and globally. Exposure to diverse cultures and people can significantly shift students' perspectives, fostering greater sensitivity and a sense of connection. According to Adarlo (2020), such exposure helps students develop a more inclusive and empathetic worldview.

On the other hand, the data also shows that the respondents have a strong sense of self-identity as Asians living in the Philippines. This aligns with the importance of recognizing one's identity in Global Citizenship Education (GCED), which focuses on understanding oneself and others. The Global Citizenship Foundation (2023) emphasizes the affective dimension of GCED, particularly in fostering positive values such as respect for diversity.

The implications of this data suggest that without exposure to other cultures and Asian identities, students may continue to feel disconnected from the global community. To foster global citizenship, it is crucial to expose students to diverse cultures and promote understanding of global interconnections, ultimately broadening their perspectives and enhancing their sense of shared humanity.

Table 4. *Global Citizenship Education Socio-Emotional Competency*

<i>How much do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements?</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1. The world is a fair place.	2.20	Disagree
2. It is important that people from different racial/ethnic backgrounds get along with each other.	3.29	Strongly Agree
3. It is important that all ethnic or racial group are treated equally.	3.53	Strongly Agree
4. Rich countries should control poor countries.	1.89	Disagree
5. Everyone should be allowed to say what they think about the government.	3.11	Agree
6. It is the government's role to protect the environment.	3.22	Agree
7. All people in society must protect the environment.	3.76	Strongly Agree
Accumulated Total Mean	3.0	Strongly Agree

The data from Table 4 presents respondents' perceptions regarding their socio-emotional competencies in Global Citizenship Education (GCED). The respondents strongly agreed, with an overall mean of 3.0, that global issues are important to address. Specifically, they strongly agreed that society must protect the environment, with a mean score of 3.76, and that people from different racial or ethnic backgrounds should get along and be treated equally, with a mean score of 3.53. This indicates that Babinian students are highly concerned about environmental protection and social equality. Their positive attitude toward the environment can be further strengthened through Global Citizenship Education, which provides students with opportunities to connect with nature and learn about environmental preservation (Yusof, S., 2020).

However, the respondents disagreed with the notion that rich countries should control poor countries, with a mean score of 1.89. This shows that the students are aware of social justice issues and reject the idea of unfair control or exploitation. Additionally, they disagreed with the statement that the world is a fair place, reflecting their negative view about global fairness. Despite this, Oxfam (2024) emphasizes that Global Citizenship Education plays a crucial role in building a fairer, safer, and more secure world.

These findings suggest that Bambinian students are not only aware of global issues but also show a strong sense of justice and equity. Their disagreement with the fairness of the world highlights the potential for action, such as activism, advocacy for policy changes, or support for social justice movements, to address perceived injustices.

Table 5. Global Citizenship Education Socio-Emotional Competency

<i>How worried are you about the following issue?</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1. Pollution in Philippines.	1.76	Quite Worried
2. Pollution in places outside of Philippines.	1.98	Quite Worried
3. Power shortages.	2.13	Quite Worried
4. Extinction of plants.	1.48	Very Worried
5. Extinction of animals.	1.33	Very Worried
6. Loss of natural resources.	1.43	Very Worried
7. Water shortages.	1.53	Very Worried
8. Climate change.	1.57	Very Worried
Accumulated Total Mean	1.65	Very Worried

The data from Table 5 presents the socio-emotional competencies of the respondents concerning environmental issues. It was found that the majority of the respondents are very worried about environmental issues, with an overall mean of 1.65. This suggests that most of the students are deeply concerned about global environmental problems such as pollution, power shortages, extinction of plants and animals, loss of natural resources, water shortages, and climate change. This highlights Bambinian students' awareness of critical environmental challenges, particularly climate change, which is seen as a "climate emergency" according to Loucks (2021). At the current rate of global warming, the sustainability of life and the state of the planet are at risk.

The respondents also expressed concern about power shortages and pollution, both in the Philippines and globally, with mean values of 2.13, 1.16, and 1.98, respectively. This indicates a strong awareness of environmental issues that affect not only their local environment but also the global community. Quiñones (2019) emphasizes the importance of understanding the environmental impacts of these issues to ensure sustainability.

These results suggest that exposure to environmental issues increases the students' concern for the environment. Additionally, a study by Boca and Saraçlı (2019) found that students engaged in environmental protection activities such as volunteering, raising awareness, participating in events, and recycling. They also contribute to using eco-friendly products and energy sources.

This implies that increasing students' exposure to environmental concerns, particularly through education, can further heighten their awareness and active participation in protecting the environment.

Table 6. Global Citizenship Education Socio-Emotional Competency

<i>How important is it for you to learn about each of the following topics?</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1. What is happening in countries near your own	3.40	Very Important
2. What is happening in the world	3.72	Very Important
3. How things that happen in other countries affect your country	3.72	Very Important
4. Understanding people that have a different race/ethnicity to you	3.61	Very Important
5. How to solve disagreements with classmates peacefully	3.47	Very Important
6. How to protect the environment	3.87	Very Important
7. How can you help to solve problems in your own community	3.55	Very Important
8. Other languages spoken in your community	3.23	Quite Important
9. Languages spoken in other countries	3.10	Quite Important
Accumulated Total Mean	3.52	Very important

The data from Table 6 indicate that respondents place significant importance on learning about global issues, current events, and conflict resolution, with an overall mean of 3.52. This suggests a strong belief among Bambinian students in the value of understanding what is happening in the world and how these events impact the Philippines.

Furthermore, the majority of respondents expressed the importance of learning about various global issues, such as understanding neighboring countries and how their events affect the Philippines (mean = 3.72), understanding different races (mean = 3.72), resolving disagreements peacefully with classmates (mean = 3.61), protecting the environment (mean = 3.47), and contributing to problem-solving within their community (mean = 3.55). These results reflect a positive disposition towards the socio-emotional competencies emphasized in Global Citizenship Education (GCED).

According to Torres (2019), Global Citizenship Education plays a critical role in promoting civic engagement by fostering knowledge, skills, and values that contribute to global peace and sustainability. The respondents' emphasis on learning to protect the environment aligns with this notion, as GCED helps students understand their responsibilities in creating a better world.

Additionally, the data revealed that some respondents consider it important to learn about the languages spoken in their community and abroad. This indicates a growing interest in understanding and connecting with other cultures. This behavior demonstrates an openness to learning about others, which can be further enhanced through GCED exposure. As Putman and Byker (2020) emphasized,

language is a vital component of global readiness. Educators' experiences abroad showed how teaching and learning different languages can foster cross-cultural connections.

Table 7. Global Citizenship Education Socio-emotional Competency

<i>Imagine a natural disaster (typhoon, earthquake, tsunami, etc.) has occurred in a country near to your own. How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1.	This has nothing to do with me.	1.92	Disagree
2.	This is only important to people who live in that country.	2.14	Disagree
3.	My country should help the people who live in that country.	3.01	Agree
4.	I would like to do something to help the people who live in that country.	2.87	Agree
5.	My school should raise money to help the people who live in that country.	2.80	Agree
<i>Accumulated Total Mean</i>		2.55	Agree

The data from Table 7 highlight the respondents' socio-emotional competencies related to Global Citizenship Education (GCED), reflecting their positive attitudes towards global issues with an overall mean of 2.55.

The results indicate that the majority of respondents agreed that their country should assist people in neighboring countries in the event of a natural disaster, and they expressed a willingness to raise money or participate in activities to help those affected, with mean scores of 3.01, 2.87, and 2.80, respectively. These findings demonstrate the respondents' strong values and willingness to support others during times of crisis, as well as their readiness to engage in school activities aimed at helping people in other countries. This highlights their empathy and sense of responsibility toward those in need, particularly during difficult times. As Bosio (2023) noted, Global Citizenship Education provides a valuable framework for reflecting critically on shared global challenges and offers meaningful ways to examine our interconnected world.

Furthermore, the respondents disagreed with the idea that natural disasters in neighboring countries are of no concern to them and should only be addressed by those living in the affected areas, with mean scores of 1.92 and 2.14, respectively. This reflects an awareness of the interconnectedness and interdependence of countries worldwide. As Mai (2019) emphasized, globalization has led to increased interdependence, where the impact of events in one country can affect others, reinforcing the need for collective action in addressing global challenges.

Table 8. Distribution of the Respondents as to the GCED Behavioral Competencies

<i>At school, have you ever done any of the following activities?</i>		<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
		<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
1.	Speak in an organize debate	44	53.01	39	46.99
2.	Present ideas to your class	77	92.77	6	7.23
3.	Speak up in classroom discussions about problems in the world	45	54.22	38	45.78
4.	Vote for class or school officers.	76	91.57	7	8.43
5.	Became a candidate for class or school officers.	39	46.99	44	53.01
6.	Participate in an activity to make the school more environmentally friendly. (Ex: water saving, recycling, etc.)	61	73.49	22	26.51

The data from table 8 revealed the data regarding respondents GCED's cognitive competencies specifically, it's about respondents participation history in discussions and debates.

Majority of the respondents were active in terms of presenting ideas to the class with the highest frequency of 77 and only 6 are not fond of presenting ideas to the class. This means that Bambinian students were well verse enough when it comes to communicating and participating in classroom discussions.. Most of the respondents are also active in terms of participating in an activity that could make the school more environmentally friendly.

However, there were several students ($f=44$) who are not that active enough in terms of participating to become a class or school officers. In line with this, University Grants Commission (2021) mentioned that GCED can recognize inconsistencies and gaps in the reasoning of others, as well as analyze and integrate data concerning global issues from diverse sources.

The data from Table 8 indicates that the statistical treatment showed no significant difference in perceived organizational culture when grouped according to educational qualifications. The p-values for working relationships (0.72), employee participation (0.30), goal clarity (0.19), management style (0.14), and organizational commitment (0.08) are all greater than the 0.05 significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis for each variable is retained, signifying no significant relationship between organizational culture and these variables when grouped by educational qualifications.

Adekanmbi and Ukpere (2021) found similar results in their study on employee participation in decision-making and perceived organizational support, reporting no significant differences based on educational qualifications. Likewise, Dyrirt and Lacap (2020) observed no significant differences in employee engagement when analyzed by educational qualifications in their research on work-life balance. Ali et al. (2021) further noted no significant difference in goal clarity in relation to educational qualifications in their investigation of humble leadership, organizational culture, and project success.

These findings imply that educational qualifications do not significantly influence employees' perceptions of organizational culture regarding working relationships, employee participation, goal clarity, management style, and organizational commitment. This highlights the need for organizations to ensure equitable treatment and opportunities for employees irrespective of their educational background. Organizations can foster a culture that values contributions from all employees, leveraging diverse educational perspectives to enhance teamwork, decision-making, and organizational success.

Table 9. *Global Citizenship Education Behavioral Competency*

<i>Will you do each of the following activities?</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1.	Tell someone who is littering to stop.	3.46	I will do this
2.	Stand up for a classmate who is being badly treated by other students.	3.69	I will do this
3.	Help other people in your community.	3.60	I will do this
4.	Make friends with someone from another country.	3.41	I will do this
5.	Encourage other people to help protect the environment.	3.53	I will do this
6.	Join a group to help protect the environment.	3.12	I might do this

The data from table 9 revealed that the respondents were willing to do some of the activities about helping other people in community, and encouraging people to help protect the environment with an overall mean of 3.47.

Majority of the respondents were very willing to stand-up for a classmate who is being badly treated (\bar{x} =3.69), and make friends with someone from another country (\bar{x} =3.41). They were likewise willing to encourage other people to help protect the environment (\bar{x} =3.41), tell someone who is littering to stop(\bar{x} =3.46), and help other people in their community (\bar{x} =3.60). This data showed that the bambinian students have positive GCED behavioural competency especially in terms of treating others fairly.

This has somehow predicted that they were responsible global citizens in the future which is the main goal of global citizenship education (Unesco 2023).

On the other hand, only few of them might do in joining a group that help protect the environment with a mean value of 3.12. Meaning, the respondents are still not that certain yet if they would be joining in group that protect the environment. Yet, if guided and trained enough in school to lead, and through GCED, students will become more competent in terms of behaviour.

Likewise, Yusof (2020) believed that GCED is likewise a civic education that includes activism and active engagement in communities, which discusses contemporary cultural, social and environmental concerns. This means that there is still a need for the respondents to be exposed to activism and active engagement in communities for them to enhance their willingness to get involved in such activities.

Table 10. *Global Citizenship Education Behavioral Competency*

<i>If you were given a chance, how likely is it that you would participate in each activity?</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Adjectival Rating</i>
1.	Vote for class or school leaders.	3.52	Very Likely
2.	Become a candidate for class/school leader.	2.53	Quite Likely
3.	Join a group of students to support an issue you agree with.	3.14	Quite Likely
4.	Speak in an organized debate.	2.88	Quite Likely
5.	Speak up in a classroom discussion about problems in the world.	3.07	Not Likely

The data from table 10 illustrated the results of the respondents GCED's behavioural competencies when it comes to their attitude toward participation in election activities, discussions or debates.

Majority of the respondents were quite likely participating to become a candidate for class or school leader, speak in an organized debate, and join a group of students to support an issue they agree with. These revealed the behaviour of the respondents that when it comes to leadership, they are somehow willing to participate though not everyone have much interest in becoming a leader as shown in the results. Their willingness to vote means they are concern with the leadership of the country in the future.

Respondents's willingness to participate in such activities would mould them to become a responsible leaders in the future. As Goryunuvang (2021) mentioned the importance of leaders as those who are capable of solving sustainability problem.

However, the respondents were not likely to speak up in a classroom discussion about problems in the world. In a similar manner, the findings from study conducted by Hwang Hyeon-kyung are consistent with Haidt's MFT in GCED contexts, implying that differences in students' perspectives on how to tackle global issues stem from their moral convictions.

Table 11. *Test of Difference on the Global Citizenship Education Competencies when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Cognitive Competency	0.285	0.593	Not Significant
Socio-Emotional Competency	0.0002	0.989	Not Significant
Behavioral Competency	0.589	0.443	Not Significant

The data from table 11 revealed the result of the test of difference on the Global Citizenship Education Competencies when grouped according to Sex.

The data revealed that there is no significant difference on GCED's cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral competencies when group according to sex.

Therefore, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis; "There is no significant difference among the respondent's GCED competencies when group according to sex."

This implies that regardless of sex, people both male and female possess these competencies as GCED promotes gender equality and appreciation of human rights (Ghosn-Chelala, M., 2020). Sex or gender has nothing to do with the development of GCED competencies nor it does influence the acquisition of such competencies. Global Citizenship education is for all people, young, old, male, and females for them to become a responsible global citizen of the world. It aims to equipped all individuals with the knowledge, skills, and behaviour necessary to address the challenges that the world is facing for a long time. This result strengthen the goal of global citizenship education to make schools a place where everyone, male or female, feels confident to take part in activities that promote global citizenship. It also highlights the idea inclusive classroom where everyone is equal.

Table 12. *Test of Difference on the Global Citizenship Education Competencies when grouped according to Age*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Cognitive Competency	10.31	0.326	Not Significant
Socio-Emotional Competency	13.02	0.162	Not Significant
Behavioral Competency	8.18	0.516	Not Significant

The data from table 12 revealed the result of the test of difference on the Global Citizenship Education Competencies when grouped according to Age.

The table above showed that there is no significant difference on GCED's cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural competencies when group according to age.

Therefore, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis; "There is no significant difference among the respondent's GCED competencies when group according according to Age."

This implies that regardless of age, GCED competencies is present in each learners even when they are still young (Bernardo, Cordel, Ricardo, Galanza, & Almonte-Acosta, S., 2022). Moreover, equipping students of all ages with the global citizenship competencies is the aim of global citizenship education specifically, in the development of a more peaceful, tolerant, inclusive, and secure local and global communities. No matter how old or young a person is, GCED competencies can be learned because GCED is for everyone. Teaching Global Citizenship Education competencies at all levels and at all ages will help create people who care about the world and act responsibly.

Table 13. *Test of Difference on the Global Citizenship Education Competencies when grouped according to Language Spoken*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Cognitive Competency	9.82	0.457	Not Significant
Socio-Emotional Competency	12.10	0.279	Not Significant
Behavioral Competency	3.36	0.972	Not Significant

The data from table 13 revealed the result of the test of difference on the Global Citizenship Education Competencies when grouped according to Language spoken.

The table above showed that there is no significant difference on GCED's cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural competencies when group according to Language spoken.

Therefore, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that regardless of the language spoken, learners possess Global citizenship education competencies as it promotes connectedness among people, build friendships, and cultural ties around the world (Sardeshpande, 2020). Language will not be a limiting factor to develop GCED competencies. Global Citizenship Education competencies can be understood and adopted by people of any language. This result highlight the importance of GCED programs in school to be created in many languages to help build a more inclusive schools where different languages are respected and included. Furthermore, this also ensures that students who speak different languages have equal potential to develop cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural competencies associated with GCED.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions can be drawn. First, the presence of learners from diverse races in Scuola Dei Bambini fosters language diversity, which is key to building relationships, friendships, and cultural ties. Additionally, the involvement of learners of various ages and sexes is crucial in promoting the objectives of Global Citizenship Education (GCED). Regarding the respondents' competencies in GCED, the study found that, in terms of cognitive competencies, respondents demonstrated a solid understanding of topics related to global citizenship, particularly the interconnectedness of countries. In terms of socio-emotional

competencies, the respondents were aware of global inequalities and social injustices, yet they lacked connections with children from other countries. In terms of behavioral competencies, while respondents displayed positive behavior toward fairness, they showed little interest in discussing global issues in class or participating in environmental protection initiatives. The null hypothesis was not rejected, as there was no significant difference in GCED competencies when grouped by demographic characteristics such as sex, age, or language spoken.

Based on the conclusions, several recommendations are offered. First, learners at Scuola Dei Bambini, regardless of sex, age, or language spoken, should be exposed to activities that enhance their GCED competencies, preparing them to become responsible global citizens. To strengthen their cognitive competencies, educators should continue to expose students to topics that raise awareness about environmental protection and global interconnectedness. Additionally, to foster the respondents' socio-emotional and behavioral competencies, the proposed program should be implemented to address gaps in their current understanding and engagement. Furthermore, GCED competencies should be nurtured in all learners, regardless of demographic factors, to ensure they are equipped with the necessary skills to be responsible global citizens. Finally, the program should be presented to the school administration for approval and implementation, ensuring that it effectively addresses the identified gaps in GCED competencies.

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